

Artificial Intelligence in Endodontics (Part I)

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The primary goal of conventional endodontic treatment is prevention and/or elimination of apical periodontitis for both mature permanent teeth and immature teeth with an open apex. Besides these goals, the objectives of endodontic treatment of immature teeth include preservation of pulp vitality and often further root maturation. The intention is to retain the tooth in its functional state and to prevent any further complications. In the recent years, there have been tremendous advancements in the endodontic diagnosis, instrumentation designs, materials, and treatment procedures that mainly intend to achieve successful endodontic care.

In order to achieve the best results, accuracy in the diagnosis and clinical decision-making is utmost important. With the advancements in the science and technology, there have been several diagnostics tools and treatment modalities that have provided new vistas in diagnosis, clinical decision-making, and planning a best therapy for endodontic diseases.

Artificial intelligence (AI) in the last few years has remarkably increased its presence and significance in a wide range of sectors, including dentistry. AI has been described as the “fourth Industrial revolution” which uses computer technology to simulate intelligent behaviour, critical thinking and decision making similar to humans. It can mimic the intelligence of humans to undertake complex predictions and decision-making in the healthcare sector, particularly in endodontics. Our daily lives are already being impacted by it, thanks to various office and practice

management software. Siri, Alexa, and other voice command devices are just a few examples of applications that have built intelligent conversational user interfaces for any device, application language, or environment using artificial intelligence.

In computer science, the study of an intelligent medium, or any machine that understands its surroundings and acts in a way that maximizes its chances of successfully reaching its goals, is referred to as AI research. The word "AI" is used when the computer imitates analytical functions, such as "learning and problem-solving", that humans frequently associate with other human brains. AI techniques have demonstrated excellent capabilities and capacities in recognizing important data patterns, leading to extensive experimentation with them as clinical trial tools, specifically to assist in decision-making for prognosis and projection, as well as each phase of diagnosis and subsequent therapy. AI has been demonstrated to increase accuracy, efficiency, and precision on par with medical experts more quickly and affordably.

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a newer technology that has been widely used in applied in dentistry. Artificial intelligence technology is mainly composed of a neural network architecture similar to the human brains and which inturn mimics the human thinking. With advancements in science and technology, there has been phenomenal developments in the application of neural networks in dentistry. Artificial intelligence technologies have been applied in dentistry mainly for diagnosis of dental diseases, treatment planning, clinical

decision-making, and prediction its prognosis. These AI-based applications applied for the various tasks have displayed to be efficient in their performance. The authors have also reported that these models are reliable, and their performance is equivalent to that of the trained experts. Several studies have also reported on the application of this newer concept for the diagnosis and treatment planning of endodontic diseases.

The majority of dental applications employ supervised learning, where the training data consists of a large number of samples, each with different characteristics or features (such as pictures of the patient, their sex, age, how many cavities they have, and so on) and determination of ground truth (e.g., whether there was a previous endodontic visit or not). The biological neuron system with a large number of connections of neurons that are utilized in "learning" is mimicked by artificial neural networks (ANNs) and is used by its algorithm to comprehend the relationship between attributes and the ground truth.

Virtual and physical (that is robotics) AI are both applicable in the field of health care. The models of AI, such as convolutional neural networks and/or artificial neural networks, have shown a variety of applications in endodontics, including studying the anatomy of the root canal system, diagnosis and prognosis, appointment scheduling, electronic health records, forecasting the viability of stem cells of the dental pulp, measuring working lengths, pinpointing root fractures and periapical lesions, forecasting the success of retreatment procedures and imaging are the main arena of the virtual type. Future applications of this technology were considered in relation to scheduling, patient care, drug-drug interactions, prognostic diagnosis, and robotic endodontic surgery. In endodontics, in terms of disease detection, evaluation, and prediction, AI has demonstrated accuracy and precision. AI can aid in the advancement of endodontic diagnosis and therapy, which can enhance endodontic treatment results. However, before incorporating AI models into routine clinical operations, it is still important to further certify the cost-effectiveness, dependability, and applicability of these models.

AI systems have the potential to revolutionize the field of medicine and dentistry by identifying solutions in managing multiple clinical problems. By developing solutions to different clinical problems, thereby making physicians' work easier, artificial intelligence has the potential to revolutionize the medical and dental disciplines. Applications of AI in the dental industry are not routine yet. However, the development of these technologies has had an impact on robotic assistance, dental image diagnostics, caries detection, radiography and pathology, and electronic recordkeeping. In line with the expansion of other dental specialties, endodontic AI research has increased. AI research in endodontics has grown in parallel to other specialties in dentistry. Regarding the use of AI, endodontists' expertise has to be updated in regard to the application of AI.

In the next issue we will discuss the current applications of AI in endodontics.....

Talk